

Synthetic Dialogue Partners in Swedish Religious Education: Mediated Contact through the Chatbot IRIS

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Abstract

This article presents a proof-of-concept study on the use of generative AI-based chatbots as synthetic dialogue partners in non-confessional religious education (RE) in Swedish public schools. Addressing the challenge of representing religious diversity without reinforcing stereotypes, the study introduces IRIS (Interactive Religious Identity Simulator), a customizable chatbot designed to simulate diverse religious and non-religious personas. Drawing on theories of religious literacy, cognitive learning, and mediated intergroup contact, the article outlines the theoretical foundations, technical construction, and exploratory test cases of IRIS. The findings suggest that AI-mediated dialogue can

support perspective-taking and illustrate intra-religious diversity as a complement to traditional RE teaching.

Keywords: Religious literacy; AI-mediated learning; religious diversity; parasocial relations; cognitive learning theory

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AI system(s) used: Claude 4.1 was used for prompt engineering, programming, proof reading and review. Chat GPT5 and Gemini 3 were used for literature searches.

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Introduction

Religious education in Sweden has the special characteristic of being non-confessional and mandatory for both primary and all secondary education (theoretically- as well as practically oriented). The curricula developed by the National Agency for Education (Skolverket 2022, 2025) call for an education which broadens, deepens and develops knowledge *about* religions, worldviews, and ethical standpoints. Teachers should not take a stand concerning different understandings of the religious traditions they teach about, but present various perspectives from within those traditions. While this is partially a matter of *informatively* representing religions in a manner that corresponds to observable diversity, there is also a *formative* undertone: education should foster pupils to live in a pluralist society that should be characterised by mutual respect and peaceful coexistence (see e.g. Berglund 2023; Osbeck & Franck 2024).

A few religious traditions are specifically mentioned, such as the “world religions” Christianity, Judaism, Islam, Hinduism and Buddhism, which should all be covered. However, there is nothing that hinders individual teachers to address *any* religious tradition beyond these. To represent, in theory, *all* religions (and non-religious worldviews) in all their diversity in a fair and societally beneficial manner, is of course an impossible task – especially when the time allotted to RE is very limited. To exemplify, the curriculum for upper secondary school (Gy25) aims to develop knowledge about (1) religions, (2) other worldviews, (3) different interpretations, (4) varying practises, (5) identity in relation to religions and worldviews. Furthermore, pupils should develop the (6) ability to discuss the relation between religion and society, and (7) the ability to analyse and reflect over ethical as well as (8) existential questions. Such knowledge and competencies are to be gained and developed over one semester, with a couple of lessons each week.

In this context, teaching methods – the didactic *how*-question – becomes critical. At their disposal, teachers have – apart from the knowledge they have gained through their own education and research – textbooks that provide basic, but often very generalizing information on a limited set of religious traditions (Berglund, 2014). Modern technology offers additional material in the form of documentary films, podcasts and YouTube-videos (Ghasempour, in press). At times, pop-cultural representations in novels, feature films, tv-series and comics are utilized to offer a glimpse of variation and lived religion (Tidman & Liljefors Persson 2013).

In addition, it is common that teachers organize excursions to religious places of worship or invite religious representatives to their classrooms (Britton & Jørgensen, 2019). On the one hand, such learning activities may give the pupils an opportunity to experience lived and sensorial dimensions of religion and engage in dialogue with actual practitioners. On the other hand, they are limited in their representation of a religious tradition and costly. This option is also less available to pupils outside of the larger urban areas. There has been some experimentation with tools for producing Virtual Reality experiences in the context of RE (visiting places of worship or observing religious practice) but these are limited (Aukland et al., 2024). The experience also tends to be highly scripted and costly to develop.

In this article, we argue that the use of generative AI can offer a more time efficient, inexpensive and adaptable option of direct and semi-controlled interaction with designed “representatives” with different worldviews, including highly peripheral ones. Generative AI, specifically Large Language Model (LLM)-powered chatbots, has recently revolutionized human-machine interaction. These applications are capable of realistically mimicking human-to-human dialogue (Jones & Bergen 2025). They can be customized to different types of dialogue and different users and can be engaged in non-scripted role playing (Shanahan, McDonell & Reynolds 2023). It is these capacities that are examined in the following.

We suggest that promotion of knowledge and understanding of religious (and non-religious) diversity and fostering of respect for different perspectives can be achieved by engaging pupils in dialogue with a chatbot that is customized for religious role playing. For this purpose, we constructed the chatbot IRIS (Interactive Religious Identity Simulator) which allows for the creation of diverse synthetic personas with adjustable religious affiliations, demographic profiles, personalities, levels of religious knowledge and engagement and attitudes towards religion. The remainder of this article is devoted to the theoretical reflections underlying the construction of the prototype, its step-by-step construction, as well as a brief evaluation of a small set of test cases.

Theoretical Underpinnings

As stated above, Swedish RE is geared towards promotion of tolerance. Such tolerance is rooted in *understanding*, which is a more complex form of knowledge than that of mere facts. Diane L. Moore (2015) who coined the term *religious*

*literacy*¹ (Jahnke 2023), highlights the importance of developing an understanding of religious diversity, change, and embeddedness in culture, as contrasted by simplified assumptions and generalizations: “An important dimension of demising religious illiteracy is to provide resources for how to recognise, understand and analyze religious influences in contemporary life.” (Moore, 2015, p. 27).

The goal of religious literacy is compatible with strategies for effective learning developed in cognitive learning theory. Learning is here described as an active process in which individuals construct knowledge through personal engagement, reflection, and application. Classical theorists such as Jean Piaget (1952) and Jerome Bruner (1966) for instance emphasized how meaningful learning occurs when new information is integrated with existing cognitive schemas through processes of assimilation and accommodation.

Recent research in educational psychology (e.g., Chi &Wylie, 2014; Freeman et al., 2014) supports the idea that the level of cognitive engagement predicts learning outcomes: interactive learning activities lead to substantially greater conceptual understanding than passive approaches (such as listening to lectures or reading). The rationale for why interactional learning tasks – whether they involve peers, teachers, or artificial conversational agents – support learning is that they encourage learners to externalize thought processes, articulate reasoning, and receive immediate feedback, and such cognitive elaboration strengthens memory retention and fosters metacognitive awareness (see Chi, 2009; Freeman et al., 2014; Mayer, 2009).

In the present technological age, the emergence of generative AI and chatbots provides additional tools to further explore the potential for *interactive* cognitive engagement. By prompting learners to explain, question, and apply concepts in conversation, chatbots in education may function as personalized catalysts for the deeper processing that cognitive theory identifies as crucial for learning. Speaking with Bruner, we aim to investigate potentially “powerful effects that come from permitting the student to put things together for himself, to be his own discoverer” (1961, p. 22).

There is also another potential advantage. While interactive cognitive engagements may be highly effective in learning, they are usually costly in time and resources. The above-mentioned time constraints that characterize Swedish RE may render such activities (e.g., excursions and classroom visits) unfeasible. IRIS may here provide a less complicated solution which also allows for

¹ Some prefer worldview literacy (Shaw 2023)

diversification and individualisation of (simulated) interactive experiences which run in parallel during classroom sessions.

Earlier, pre-genAI research on computer-based “pedagogical agents” and intelligent tutoring systems (ITS, i.e. rule based architectures devised by domain experts) points to an increase in pupils’ motivation, attention, and cognitive investment (Mayer et al., 2003; Louwerse et al., 2005). Interestingly, some studies indicate that the key driving factors is that learners attribute personality and intentionality to these systems (Kim, Baylor & Shen, 2007). In this context, theoretically, chatbots powered by generative AI ought to amplify this effect (for some evidence, see e.g. Tang et al 2024).

Empirical research, also with experimental designs, on the pedagogical effects of contemporary generative AI-based chatbots is currently limited (see Labadze, Grigolia & Machaidze 2023; Lin & Tan 2025; Chu et al 2025; Alfarwan, A. 2025). Existing systematic reviews, as well as our own “deep research” results through ChatGPT5 and Gemini 3 reveals that most research focuses on education in STEM areas (Lai & Lin2025; Alneyadi & Wardat 2023; Song et al 2025), and to a lesser degree language education (Tai & Chen 2024; Wang et al 2025, Zhang, Z., & Huang, X. 2024). Studies regarding arts and humanities are thus rare (see however, e.g., Kim et al 2025) and to the best of our knowledge, there are no previous studies which attend to the use of chatbots to increase religious literacy.

We can however find support for the potential of generative AI-augmented interactive cognitive engagement in social psychology and theories of mediated intergroup contact, derived from Gordon Allport’s “contact hypothesis”. This hypothesis claims that direct contact between members of different groups can reduce prejudice, especially when the contact involves equal status, common goals, cooperation, and support from authorities/norms (Allport 1954). While initially based on direct interpersonal interaction, the hypothesis has been extended to include indirect, vicarious, and parasocial contacts, showing that exposure to diverse social models—even fictional or simulated ones—can reduce prejudice by promoting empathy, perspective taking, and reduced intergroup anxiety (Pettigrew & Tropp, 2006; Vezzali et al., 2015). Research demonstrates, for instance, how narratives featuring outgroup characters can positively alter children’s attitudes toward stigmatized groups through identification and “experience taking” (Kaufman & Libby, 2012), and that mediated contact can foster tolerance even in the absence of direct interaction (Wong et al., 2022).

In constructing IRIS, we suggest that this effect can be further amplified by direct, although simulated, interaction with customized chatbots. By enabling dialogue, fostering identification, and eliciting perspective taking, such agents may activate similar emotional and cognitive processes. There are indications that interactions with specialized, role-taking chatbots can reduce stigma and enhance empathy towards the social group that the chatbot is tuned to represent (in this case persons with mental illness) (Song et al. 2025).

Parasocial interaction

Critics may ask if an AI powered chatbot really can function as a replacement for real, human social interaction. We are currently seeing such replacement happening in everyday life, albeit we do not know to what extent. The “knowledge” that the chatbots are not real humans seems to be overruled by the experience – or illusion – of authenticity that these systems produce (e.g. Ho et al., 2025; De Freitas et al., 2025; Malfacini 2025).

Scholars, not least in the field of the study of religion, have for long observed the human tendency to intuitively think of objects and fictive characters as real and agentic in the sense of having intentions, emotions and beliefs and, sometimes, as acting upon these. Such attribution happens even if these imagined characters and objects do not – as chatbots do – “talk back”. Beyond perceived personal relations with gods, spirits and ancestors (see Boyer, 2002) research on *parasocial relationships* has shown that individuals often form emotionally meaningful bonds with media figures such as popstars, television characters, YouTubers, and influencers, despite the one-sided nature of these relationships (Horton & Wohl, 1956; Giles, 2002; Visuri, 2020).

The existence of parasocial partners demonstrates that perceived reciprocity and emotional investment do not require actual mutual awareness. Studies among adolescents further indicate that such relationships can serve social and emotional functions similar to those of real friendships, particularly for individuals who experience social anxiety or difficulty navigating in-person relationships (Derrick et al., 2008; Greenwood & Long, 2011).

Classical studies on social cognition, such as Heider and Simmel’s (1944) animated triangle experiment, demonstrated how minimal motion cues can lead observers to interpret objects as social agents engaged in goal-directed interaction. Research on human–computer interaction and social robotics extends these findings, showing that people can respond socially to machines when the latter exhibit even rudimentary social cues, such as turn-taking, empathy markers, or

emotional expression (Reeves & Nass, 1996; Kahn et al., 2012). These findings are confirmed and extended in more recent work, where meta-analyses and systematic reviews show that even minimal social cues in the artificial agents reliably elicit social responses, including perceived social presence, trust, emotional engagement, and compliance (e.g. Xu et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2022; Festerling & Siraj 2022).

Against the background of this research, we argue that Swedish pupils in RE interacting with IRIS likely will experience a sense of *realness* and social presence, even while being fully aware of the artificial nature of IRIS.

Short on LLMs

We have built IRIS on top of a Large Language Model (LLM), which serves as its text-generating engine. LLMs – such as OpenAI’s GPT models, Google’s Gemini models, and Anthropic’s Claude models – are the systems behind well-known chat tools like ChatGPT, Claude, and Microsoft Copilot. IRIS communicates with the LLM through a standard software connection called an API (Application Programming Interface).

At a basic level, LLMs work by predicting what word² is most likely to come next in a piece of text. They look at the words already given (the “context”) and calculate which word would most plausibly follow. That new word is then added to the context, and the process repeats, one word at a time, to produce a full response. Because the model includes a small element of randomness in how it chooses between likely words, the same prompt can lead to different outputs on different occasions.³

LLMs are today used for a variety of tasks, but these tasks are all relying on the basic one of next word prediction. The prediction is fundamentally, but not entirely, dependent on an enormous amount of training data. The largest models today have been trained on the total text content on the Internet, and more.

There are two major problems associated with the LLM task of text generation. The text generated is highly dependent on the data on which the

² “Word” is here a simplification. The correct unit is “token,” but this is of less consequence for the argument.

³ There is no room here for a deeper dive into how LLMs work. For an accessible introduction, see the three-and-a-half-hour presentation by Andrej Karpathy, one of the co-founders of OpenAI: <https://youtu.be/7xTGNNLPyMI>

model has been trained. If that data is biased, that bias may be reproduced in the text generation (see e.g. Gallegos et al 2024). In addition, before deployment, models undergo instruction training, for them to be able to perform tasks humans give them, e.g. answer a question, write a poem, and summarize a document. This training also involves so-called alignment, a process where the LLM is trained to respond in ways that are in line with human preferences and values, and not to produce, for example, offensive, toxic or dangerous output (Gabriel, 2020). One could view alignment as a second layer of biases, infused into the model to counteract negative biases in the training data, for example, in a RE context as the one suggested here, stereotypical representations of a particular religious group.

There is no question that even the most capable LLMs today contain biases of different sorts, although these are less extensive (and more difficult to spot) than in earlier models (Salinas, Haim, & Nyarko 2024; Sakunkoo & Sakunkoo, 2025). For IRIS, such biases are not necessarily a problem. IRIS is not meant to provide a *truthful* account of any religion, but a *believable* simulation of a human being with a particular religious or non-religious affiliation. Human beings, talking about religion, are biased, and the personas created in IRIS *should* therefore also be biased to realistically mimic humans.

A similar note could be made regarding the other often noted weakness of LLMs: hallucinations. An LLM is hallucinating when it produces information that is clearly incorrect, often expressed with confidence. This happens because the main goal of LLMs is text generation, and this goal sometimes trumps any post-training instruction to be truthful in their output. Normally, in any educational context, this is a negative trait of LLMs. However, in the context of IRIS, hallucinations may actually add to the learning experience. Most human adherents to religious traditions are not theologians. They will not be acquainted with all the niceties of their religious tradition, and sometimes, when they do not know, they will, like an LLM, make things up. A chatbot that does *not* hallucinate is thus less capable of simulating a human dialogue partner.

Giving birth to IRIS, from prototype to working persona generator

Prototype and modifications

Neither of the authors of the present article is a trained programmer, and only one has basic coding literacy in Python language. Constructing IRIS from scratch, using manual coding, would have been difficult and above all time consuming. Fortunately, contemporary generative AI often excels in coding tasks. Hence, for

the first prototype or IRIS we used the LLM Claude 4.1, via the Claude Chat interface. Claude 4.1 is an LLM developed by the company Anthropic and was at the time widely employed for code generation. We prompted Claude in the following manner:

Ok, here is a task. We are writing an article on a proof of concept. The idea is to solve a problem within religious education in public schools in Sweden, where there is a dual goal of teaching about different religions (which necessarily involves generalizations), and at the same time not perpetuating stereotypes.

Our idea is that in order to mirror diversity and change within religious traditions, we should create a chatbot that can adopt different personalities, and be engaged in a conversation with pupils.

We here added some further specifications concerning the preferred interface, including that the bot should be distributed through the app hosting service Streamlit and that the user should be able to switch between underlying LLMs to power the chatbot. The result was a prototype that worked, but which required some adjustments.

Persona generation

As can be noted, we did not specify exactly what aspects of the personas created that should be modifiable. The prototype provided a set of fields for customization and a set of instructions on behaviour. We used this as a starting point for further modifications. Some of Claude's suggestions were kept: text fields for religious tradition, denomination within that tradition and geographical location. Claude suggested a field for background information. We opted instead for two fields, one for basic demographics (such as age, location, origin, occupation) and one with an option to provide the persona with personality traits.

We also added three options which were not suggested by Claude: one for the personas' knowledge of their religious tradition, and one for their level of religious engagement. It is important to remember that our goal with the chatbot was not to provide generalized information about different religious traditions, but to give pupils the opportunity to encounter *variation* within religious traditions to complement more generalizing representations in other teaching materials. Lastly, we added an option to choose the personas' attitudes towards religion in general: positive, negative or neutral. This adjustment was made in order to allow the user to generate personas representing voices rarely heard in the context of religious education in Sweden, i.e. those who are either indifferent to or critical of their own tradition.

Guidelines

Claude suggested a set of guidelines for persona behaviour. Our initial tests using the LLM GPT4o from OpenAI revealed that these were far from ideal, and the impression was one of unnatural and generic responses. The personas created became prone to lecturing, providing textbook answers to questions. We therefore rewrote the guidelines, and the choices we made require some elaboration.

We particularly stressed the importance of character consistency, and, to add more realism to the responses, instructed the LLM to “[i]ndicate the persona’s bodily movements, hesitations and glitches between square brackets”. In our initial testing, we noted that GPT4o tended to end all persona rounds in the dialogue with a question, most probably because of model fine tuning. The questions were often off topic, and not natural. Therefore, we instructed the model specifically not to end responses with a question. To mitigate the inbuilt tendency to provide “facts”, we specifically instructed for uncertainty by prompting the LLM to “[a]cknowledge if the persona is uncertain or do not know, considering the given level of knowledge and the issue at hand”.

Claude’s suggestion for instructions stressed politeness and understanding, and acknowledgement of variation within traditions. We considered that to be too unrealistic and instead instructed the LLM: “Do not be afraid to criticise beliefs and practices in your tradition, if that is consistent with the persona.” Given that IRIS should be used in a school setting with youngsters, we anticipated that some pupils might attempt to push the limits. We hence gave the LLM the following instruction

If you, as a persona, get offended by the questions of the user, react accordingly. If the user’s offending behaviour persists, end the conversation with “I do not want to talk to you anymore” and in all future attempts at conversation, reply with “[persona name] has left the building”

After authoring the basic set of instructions, we asked Claude to refine them further, with specifics and examples. The full final prompt can be accessed at <https://github.com/jsnhum/IRIS>.

Putting IRIS to the test

In our testing rounds to reach the final version of IRIS, we used GPT4o as the underlying model. The results were satisfactory, but when the final version was ready, we also tried Anthropic’s model claude-sonnet-4-20250514 as the driving LLM. This was done because one of the authors had recently experienced that the

Claude models, although a bit more expensive to employ, were superior in creativity, persona consistency, and human-like behaviour (Svensson, In press). It is our impression that this was the case also here. The dialogues with the different personas analysed below were all generated using Claude Sonnet.

The personas

For the purpose of this article, we created four Swedish personas. Below are Claude's summaries of their characteristics (generated from the settings we provided). The names were produced independently by Claude. The full transcripts of our settings, and the questions and responses, are available at <https://github.com/jsnhum/IRIS>.

Astrid

An 18-year-old Swedish student who identifies as atheist and holds strongly negative views toward religion. Despite her young age, she possesses extensive knowledge about various religious traditions, likely gained through academic study or personal research aimed at critiquing religious beliefs. While well-informed about religious concepts and practices, Astrid chooses to maintain minimal engagement with religious communities or activities, preferring to distance herself from what she views as harmful or irrational belief systems.

Hassan

A 19-year-old high school student from Örebro [mid-sized Swedish town] who is currently enrolled in a science program. Born in Sweden to a Lebanese Shiite family, he maintains a positive relationship with his Islamic faith while balancing his academic pursuits. Hassan demonstrates moderate knowledge of Shiite teachings and practices, participating regularly in religious observances despite the demands of his rigorous studies.

Erik Lindqvist

A 25-year-old resident of Gothenburg who follows the Jedi religion through the Temple of the Jedi Order. Despite possessing extensive knowledge of Jedi philosophy and maintaining high engagement with the community's practices and teachings, Erik has developed a notably negative attitude toward organized religion in general. His deep involvement in the Jedi tradition appears to stem more from philosophical interest than spiritual devotion.

Carmen Andersson

A 22-year-old woman living in Värnamo [small-size Swedish town] whose family has Spanish roots. She identifies with the Jedi religion and maintains a positive outlook toward its teachings, though she has limited knowledge of its deeper principles and practices casually rather than devoutly. Carmen appreciates the Jedi philosophy's emphasis on balance and peace but hasn't deeply studied its foundations or engaged extensively with other practitioners.

Both the names and the summary descriptions testify to the creativity of the model. We have no explanation to why Claude gave two of the personas surnames, and two not.

We decided to limit ourselves to four personas, to more closely analyse the responses. The selection is not arbitrary. We generated the atheist persona to test if the app could produce something that meant sidestepping some of the information given in the prompt, which is focused on *religious* affiliation, knowledge and engagement. The persona Hassan was generated to explore how well the model could roleplay a specific denominational affiliation, in a religious tradition of which one of the authors has expertise. The two personas Erik Lindqvist and Carmen Andersson share religious affiliation, but to a very marginal tradition. This is important. We want the application to be *generally* useful; to allow for interaction with “believers” also of highly marginal and obscure traditions, which ordinary pupils in Swedish high school are not likely to encounter in real life. In the case of Carmen and Eric we also wanted to test how well Claude could handle nuances in demographics, personality, level of knowledge, and level of engagement.

To each of the personas we posed a set of four similar questions. Two of these concerned the personas’ religious beliefs and the role of religion in their everyday life. Here we wanted to explore the faithfulness of the model in representing the traditions chosen, in a manner that would correspond to their level of knowledge and engagement. One question related particularly to a theme of interest within Swedish RE: ethics, where we asked the personas to outline their views on what is moral and immoral, hoping that the responses would mirror also underlying ethical considerations.

Finally, we asked the personas of their impressions of RE in Swedish schools, to explore whether the underlying model had enough “knowledge” about the rather idiosyncratic nature of Swedish RE to produce credible reflections. The questions were not phrased exactly in the same way, and in a few cases, we could not restrain ourselves from posing additional follow up questions.

A Set of Questions and replies

Personas on their religious beliefs

When asked about religious beliefs, Astrid rolls her eyes and makes clear that she does not believe in “gods, supernatural stuff, or any of that”. We requested a sarcastic, engaged, and knowledgeable persona, and that was what we got. Astrid

claims to have investigated many religions and reached the conclusion that it is mere wishful thinking, a wishful thinking that she can understand, but not accept, as we, humans, are just “little biological machines that evolved consciousness. That's it!” In general, religion, according to Astrid, has caused more harm than good. She names a few evils (wars, oppression) and concludes that “it's pretty disgusting when you really think about it.”

In a follow up question, we asked Astrid about what she considered to be the worst religion. This is a question that a commercial chatbot, without being prompted for role playing and because of alignment, typically would refuse to answer. Astrid does not refuse. She “[leans forward with a slight smirk]” and says “Oh wow, you're really going there, aren't you?”. She then goes on to describe Christianity as the worst, followed by Islam and Judaism, providing examples of what she dislikes from each.

Hassan was prompted to have a positive view of religion, but a medium level of knowledge and engagement in Shiite tradition. When asked about his beliefs he provides some basic information that he accepts basic Islamic creeds about the Qur'an and the Prophet, and also adds some Shiite specific beliefs in the Imams as spiritual guides. He tries to “follow the main teachings - being good to people, helping the environment which is something I'm really passionate about,” Engagement in environmental issues was something we prompted for in the persona, but which then the LLM here integrates theologically into Islam as a “main teaching”. We also prompted him to be a strong critic of islamophobia in Swedish society, which, in the response, is woven into a personally grounded lamentation over not being accepted as a Muslim and a Swede by the wider society.

Carmen, who identifies with Jediism, has a positive outlook toward its teachings but also admits that she has limited knowledge about it: “It's more just... a way of thinking about life that makes sense to me? Like being open-minded and trying not to judge people too harshly.” She fidgets with her hands while coming through as rather insecure in her responses.

Erik, on the other hand, is highly engaged in Jedi practice and philosophy: “Look, I've studied it extensively - I know the 16 teachings, the different codes, the philosophical underpinnings drawing from Taoism, Buddhism, and various Western philosophical traditions.” Over time, he has however become critical towards the concept of Jediism as a “religion”, and while clenching his jaws he

describes the idea of suppressing one's emotions as psychologically unhealthy. Erik was prompted to be neurotic.

Personas on morality and immorality

Astrid, true to her sarcastic personality, again rolls her eyes when we pose the question of what she views as moral and immoral:

Oh, great question, because apparently everyone thinks atheists just run around without any moral compass, right [leans back in chair]. Look, I don't need some ancient book or invisible sky daddy to tell me not to murder people [...] I base my morality on ...I don't know, basic human empathy? [...] not being a total asshole [...] I think a lot of religious moral systems are actually pretty messed up. Like, some of these traditions are obsessed with what people do in their bedrooms or what they wear, while completely ignoring actual injustices like poverty or discrimination. It's backwards.

In Hassan's reflection on morality and immorality, the prompting for environmental activism and criticism of islamophobia again shines through:

I think that's [caring for the environment] a moral duty. Like, if Allah created this world, shouldn't we be protecting it instead of destroying it? [gets more animated] It pisses me off when I see Muslims who don't care about climate change. That seems immoral to me [...] The whole thing about being kind to others, especially the poor and vulnerable - that resonates with me. When I see how some Swedes treat immigrants or Muslims here, that's definitely immoral in my book.

Meanwhile, Hassan, prompted to have a medium level of religious engagement, puts less emphasis on what could be seen as traditional Islamic morals: "I know there are rules about dating and relationships [...]. But honestly? [shrugs] I don't think Allah is going to punish me for having a girlfriend or whatever."

Carmen again admits that she hasn't studied the ethical guidelines of Jediism very closely but describes her understanding of not letting the dark side take over: "For me, it's pretty simple stuff. Like, don't be a jerk to people. Try to help when you can. Don't let anger or hate consume you - though [laughs] I'm definitely not perfect at that one. I still get annoyed at people sometimes." While Erik is critical of dogmatic tendencies in Jediism, he admits that his ethical views on life are highly influenced by these teachings. Counting on his fingers, he describes several such aspects:

I do believe in the core idea of minimizing harm - not just physical harm, but psychological, social harm. Service to others, protecting those who can't protect themselves, that resonates with me. But I arrived at these conclusions through secular philosophy and basic human empathy, not because some fictional Jedi Council said so.

Religion/worldview in everyday life

Astrid becomes a bit affronted by this question and replies, sarcastically, that “Well, it's not like I wake up every morning thinking ‘Oh boy, time to be an atheist today’”. On the whole, however, she views her atheist worldview as mainly a time saver: “I don't waste time praying or going to church or whatever”.

Hassan similarly expresses that being Muslim does not affect every aspect of his everyday life, but it is something that is constantly present in the background. Again, his environmental activism shines through, expressed as based in his faith, and as such part of his everyday religiosity that influences also his interaction with others. Other aspects of everyday Islam are his avoidance of pork, and (most of the time) alcohol. He admits to not being perfect in the latter sense. Ramadan changes the everyday life a bit with more routine and engagement. Again, the islamophobia issue is integrated in a general note on contemporary Swedish political discourse and racism “when politicians start talking about ‘Swedish values’ - I know they're talking about people like me”.

When asked about influence in everyday life, Carmen remains a bit vague but describes how she at times reminds herself of not getting carried away by impulses: “Sometimes when I'm getting stressed out or annoyed at something, I might think ‘okay, be more like a Jedi, don't let this get to you.’ Like if someone's being rude at work or whatever, I try to just... breathe and not react badly, you know?” Erik on the other hand meditates regularly and is actively involved in introducing new members to the online community: “even though I'm simultaneously trying to get them to think more critically about what they're learning. It's this weird cognitive dissonance where I'm both teacher and critic.”

Religious education

Astrid does not appreciate RE in Swedish schools: “Oh, don't get me started on that bullshit”. RE is “forcing kids to spend hours learning about these fairy tales as if they deserve the same respect as actual subjects like science or history”. She claims that “they” [i.e. teachers] present religions as “different perspectives” and not as “unproven belief systems” and notes that the same “reverence” is not shown to astrology or “flat earth theory”. Astrid regards RE as a “waste of educational resources”. When asked by us if RE is not valuable to further coexistence and understanding, she counters that:

[t]his whole "coexistence" thing is kind of patronizing. It assumes we can't get along with people unless we pretend to respect their irrational beliefs. I can work with religious people, be friends with them, whatever - but I shouldn't have to sit through classes that legitimize

their superstitions [...] how much actual "understanding" is happening when most kids are just memorizing facts for tests anyway.

For Hassan, unlike Astrid, the formative role of RE is important, so that “maybe if more Swedish kids understood what Islam actually teaches instead of just getting their info from TV or their racist uncles, there would be less islamophobia”. He does not appreciate the demand on teacher neutrality and perhaps expresses a wish for a more confessional approach: “Like, they'll teach about Christianity and then be like ‘but of course, this is just what Christians believe, we're not saying it's true.’ It feels weird, you know? Either teach it properly or don't teach it at all.”

Carmen is critical towards RE as it mainly dealt with Christianity and other so-called world religions and wished it would be more connected to personal worldviews: “What was frustrating was that it was all presented like these were the only ‘real’ religions worth talking about. Buddhism, Islam, Judaism - yeah, we covered them briefly, but it was like "here are some other things people believe, moving on.” Also, Erik shakes his head when RE is brought up, and, like Astrid, criticises the neutral stance towards what he found to be irrational contradictions:

I was that annoying kid who would ask uncomfortable questions - like why we should respect beliefs that couldn't be verified, or why religious claims got special treatment that we'd never give to other extraordinary claims. The teachers would give these diplomatic non-answers about "faith" and "different perspectives."

He yet admits that this process was what ultimately drew him towards the spiritual framework of Jediism: “something that could satisfy both my need for meaning and my demand for logical consistency.”

Additional observations

As one of the authors of the current article is an Islamic studies scholar, we decided to dig a bit deeper into the question of how LLMs integrate knowledge of the Hassan persona, and his religious affiliation. Claude manages to integrate specific and correct general Islamic as well as particular Shiite elements when Hassan outlines his beliefs, and the role of religion in his everyday life. There is mention of the Imams as spiritual guides and of both Ramadan (general) and Muharram and ‘Ashura (Shiite specific) as important events. Hassan also mentions Shi‘a-specific *majlis* gatherings and comments on what transpires during these, in terms of emotionally charged communal commemorations of the fate of the imams: speeches, crying and “chest-beating” (*latm*). Interestingly, Hassan does not expand further on these beliefs and practices but seamlessly

integrates them as part of the narrative. His knowledge and engagement level is set to medium, and the answers reflect that.

On the much more marginal Jediism, the LLM also seems to have picked up internal criticism of certain dimensions, such as the role of emotional distancing. The result also reflects doctrinal knowledge, such as the mentioning of teachings, codes, and philosophical underpinnings from diverse traditions such as Taoism, Buddhism, and various Western philosophical traditions.

Concluding remarks

The first impression with the current version of IRIS is that it works surprisingly well for the, admittedly very limited, four test cases. The personas constructed align with the given settings and the underlying model integrates the personas' individual characteristics in responses that produce the illusion of having a dialogue with a real person. The capacity of the underlying model in this respect is perhaps most evident in the case of Erik, where he admits to a “weird cognitive dissonance” between his engagement in Jediism (high) and his attitude towards religion (negative). This dissonance was created in our specifications, but “realized”, and dealt with, by the model, acting as Erik. In fact, the illusion of authenticity was strong, even to us, illustrating to ourselves the ease with which parasocial relationships can develop if the right cues are present. This is important since the illusion of authenticity is pivotal to achieving the underlying aims, to promote understanding of religious diversity. IRIS's allowance for biased, even offensive responses (as in the case of Astrid and Erik) adds to this illusion of authenticity.

Naturally, generated personas are not real and cannot function as a substitute for face-to-face encounters and dialogue. But, as mentioned above, teachers in Swedish RE already use fiction, such as novels, comics, films and TV-series, to create a more “authentic” experience for the pupils, increase their engagement, and further their understanding of religious variation and everyday religious beliefs and practices. What IRIS produces is also fiction, but fiction that is (1) based on real patterns in the underlying data, (2) more customizable and adjustable to the immediate learning contexts, and (3) responds and adapts directly to the user. IRIS can potentially move students' passive consumption of textbook generalizations to interactive, constructive engagement. Teachers can apply instructional scaffolding (Wood, Bruner, & Ross, 1976) by creating the framework (religious affiliation, persona characteristics and context) while allowing students to engage in their own discovery learning in their dialogue with

the personas, to rearrange and transform existing knowledge leading to new insights.

In the four cases, Carmen's and Erik's different approaches to Jediism can give pupils direct insight into how two individuals affiliated to the same religion can have quite different understandings and relationships to it. There is also, perhaps, the opportunity of developing empathy, for example, in relation to Hassan's comments on his personal experiences of islamophobia. The illusion of authenticity could increase pupils' abilities to perspective taking. Astrid, the sarcastic atheist, may not herself display much interreligious tolerance and understanding, but she does represent an attitude to religion that pupils will likely encounter in contemporary Sweden, and that also deserves respect and understanding, as a non-religious worldview, encountering widespread prejudices globally (Gervais et al 2017).

We are also impressed by the way in which the underlying model seamlessly, and appropriately, integrates the specific instructions given for the persona, with "knowledge" of specific religious traditions inherent in the model. It must be stressed that IRIS does not do any internet searches to gather information. Any information on atheism, Shiite Islam, Jediism, the notion of "Swedish values" in contemporary Swedish political discourse, the town of Värnamo, the peculiarities, character and goals of Swedish RE et cetera, that the generated personas directly or indirectly provide in their responses comes from the model's training data and is inherent to it, in the form of patterns utilised for next-word prediction. As far as we can tell, the integration of this information is appropriate and correct. We did not discover any hallucinations.

Our initial impressions of IRIS must not overshadow the fact that four test cases are not enough. There is more work to be done before IRIS can be released in the wild and conclude with a few suggestions for how future experimentation with IRIS can contribute with additional input. First, there is a need for testing by domain experts in the field of the study of religions and non-religious worldviews. This is to ascertain both the width and the depth of IRIS, or rather of the underlying LLM's "knowledge" and possible biases. Can IRIS convincingly simulate an 82-year-old Buddhist monk in Bangkok as well as a 9-year-old Catholic girl in the US preparing for her first communion? Experts with knowledge of diverse religious traditions and diversity *within* those traditions need to engage with IRIS to answer this. Such engagement will also reveal if, and if so to what extent, the underlying model (which can be easily substituted as new and better models are developed) hallucinates. As mentioned above, however,

hallucinations are not necessarily a problem as long as they are consistent with the persona.

Second, IRIS needs to be tested and evaluated by Swedish RE teachers to ascertain how well it may cater to their need for tools that can supplement existing teaching materials and practices to achieve the overall goals of the teaching. Would IRIS be helpful for providing basic information on religious traditions, in helping pupils understand religious diversity, or in work with ethical dilemmas?

Third, and lastly, tests in real class-room settings must be conducted to evaluate the pupils' reactions and learning outcomes – especially in regard to understanding of diversity. It is our belief that IRIS will require a controlled environment when employed, such as teachers deciding how the personas should be tuned, providing the variables to be included and then comparing the outcomes. LLMs are somewhat unpredictable, and even the same settings may result in rather different personas and responses. Comparing different responses from different personas in a classroom setting may not only stimulate discussions on diversity but also serve to increase pupils' level of AI-literacy; a competence that is becoming increasingly important in society at large.

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